

Title:

“Urban labs as a new form of public governance: public value creation and its measurement”

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Abstract of Manuscript

The world is constantly changing. In this transitional turmoil, urban labs emerge as a solution to current and future urban challenges. One of their main objectives is co-creation of public value. The article examines the concept of public value creation in urban lab projects. It attempts to explain “what, how and for whom” it is created. After presenting the elusive definitions of both urban labs and public value, the article introduces a method in order to answer the research question. Four projects from two urban labs namely, M-Lab in Maastricht and Stadslab 2050 in Antwerp, serve as a case-study. Moreover, the article presents a tailored tool that measures public value creation in the projects. The results prove that evaluative processes are highly affected by different perspectives, stakes, as well as the moment one expresses their opinion. Time possesses a substantial role, which needs to be acknowledged in pursuit of avoiding any misinterpretations. The numbers do not lead directly to a decision. It is up to the practitioners to determine their meaning based on pre-set conditions. The method is highly flexible and can be tailored to every circumstance, which leaves space for future improvements. What should not be forgotten, is that urban labs and their projects are dynamic processes and they should be considered as such and assessed in every step of their progress.

Keywords: Urban labs, living lab, city lab, public value, value creation, value measurement, public administration, local management

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The world is constantly changing. Human society is both the producer and the receiver of transitional developments. Problems that appear globally can be better resolved locally. Urban labs rise as a new approach towards such complex matters. They are inextricably linked with present and future policies that call for a balance between society, environment and economy; a balance that will lead to a more sustainable future. Local authorities do not decide for themselves. Their actions and activities affect directly the society and all the actors included in it. Thus, it is reasonable to introduce a new form of governance that embraces all stakeholders in an active manner. Public value indicates how a project contributes to the common good and enhances the engagement of different actors within their community. Several researchers attempted to find a way of measuring public value creation. It is of great difficulty to develop a method or tool that measures effectively public value in a way that will not be criticized by its users or researchers. It is rightly recognized that applying theory to practice and translating concepts and theoretical approaches into scores are of substantial difficulty, but also necessity for providing the information needed in future policy making and governance.

Local authorities that consider establishing urban labs, as well as researchers and other actors, face a substantial knowledge gap that constraints their efforts of implementing and/or improving an urban-lab initiative. Thus, more research on public value as such, as well as on its measurement is essential. Further information will provide useful insights to those who need to weigh future decisions.

Sustainable Development

Sustainable development is a concept that penetrates our contemporary world. There are numerous definitions, but this particular research is based on Brundtland's report:

“Sustainable Development is the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (WCED, 1987).

According to the report, there are three main pillars of sustainability that represent the main aspects of human life on the planet. These are economic growth, environmental protection and social equality (Brundtland, 1987). All three are interrelated and interdependent. Thinking schematically, they could be placed on the vertices of a triangle. A change in one of them affects the other two sides. Of course, in reality the described system is much more complex than in this simple theoretical approach. Still, this explanation provides a useful first insight on the interlinkage between human society, its activities and the environment. In order to find a balance between the pillars, it seems necessary to adapt the governing structures. Dominant practices where a group of people used to decide for the whole society seem to belong to the past.

Aims, Objectives and Research Question

The aims of the research are to:

- Examine what, how and for whom public value is created in urban labs.
- Define indicators that are relevant for measuring/evaluating public value creation as they help understand how different actors perceive the concept of public value.
- Develop a method or tool for measuring public value (creation) in urban lab projects.

The research focused on public value creation in four projects developed in two urban labs (M-Lab Maastricht, Stadslab 2050 Antwerp). They served as a case study that provided substantial information for answering the **research question “How do urban labs create**

public value?". Afterward, I developed a method that measures public value creation in urban labs.

Methods

Research Strategy

A comparative case study has been completed in order to answer the research question. Therefore, a number of completed and currently running projects¹ established by two urban labs, M-Lab in Maastricht and Stadstad 2050 in Antwerp, have been examined. There are specific criteria based on which, I chose the projects. Firstly, they had to be implemented under the "urban lab" label. In addition, citizens should be involved either as "producers" or receivers of public value since the latter had to affect the society as a whole in order to be considered "public".

M-Lab emerged in 2012 as a solution to the consequences of the economic crisis a few years earlier, which affected both the economic and demographic data of the area. It is a temporary non-legal platform that is based on the development of new coalitions between different actors, experimentation and learning (de Kraker, Cörvers, Scholl, & van Wanroij, 2016; van Wanroij, personal communication, May 3, 2017). The research examined two projects namely, Brandweerkazerne and Operatie Steenbreek. The first aimed in repurposing an empty building, whereas the latter attempts to stop the trend of paving domestic gardens in order to create environmental awareness.

The second urban lab was Stadslab 2050. It started in 2011 as a platform with the aim of transforming Antwerp into a sustainable city in the long-term. The urgency of becoming sustainable though, convinced the local politicians to establish it as an urban lab. Regarding its projects, Amador was a shared kitchen that ran from October 2015 till May 2016. Its main goals were to enhance social relationships in the city and create environmental awareness in relation to food. The second project, 500 Woningen Renoveren was co-initiated by Ecohuis²

and Stadslab. It has a double aim: firstly, to renovate apartments towards a more energy efficient mode; at the same time, the initiators would like to affect people's behavior and make them act in a more sustainable manner.

Data and Analysis

A mixture of quantitative and qualitative data has been collected. Open-ended and closed-ended questions have been used. Concerning the amount of data collection, it was important to have at least one representative of each municipality that "hosts" the examined urban lab projects as they have considerable knowledge about the projects and can provide useful information for the research.

Returning to the data collection, a number of stakeholders, 2-5³ from each project have been interviewed in order to gain a better view of the public value created. As stakeholders, I considered all kinds of legal and non-legal entities as well as individuals who participate in a project and are affected and at the same time affect the creation of public value, in other words, anyone who has a stake. They could be people directly involved like the initiator of the project, urban professionals, such as companies, NGOs, SMEs and of course, individuals. Projects generate public value, which affects individuals that have been both actively and non-actively involved. Citizens tend to belong to both categories and hence, have different views on the examining project based on the role they possess.

Structure

Chapter 1 introduced the reader to the topic of the article. It provided general information about the core concepts, urban labs and public value, and presented the methods that have been used in order to answer the research question "How do urban labs create public value". The following chapters make a deeper analysis on the aforementioned. Chapter 2 explains more the main concepts. Chapter 3 focuses on the presentation of the methodology and the

development of the tool. Chapter 4 analyzes and compares the research findings. Finally, the article closes by resuming and extracting conclusions about the results and the lessons that can be provided to the readers.

Chapter 2

Urban Labs and Public Value Creation

This chapter provides further information about the main concepts examined namely, urban labs and public value. It examines some of the different aspects that appear in the literature. Moreover, the floor is given to those who attempted to develop a tool in pursuit of measuring public value.

Urban Labs

“Urban labs” is a generic term that includes among others, Living Labs and City Labs (Voytenko et al., 2016). The URB@Exp report (Scholl et al., 2017) presents thirteen types of labs acknowledging the fact that the list is not definitive⁴. As a result, the term urban lab covers a wide range of different forms of local governance.

To begin with, “there is no uniform definition of living labs” (Schliwa, 2013; Voytenko et al., 2016). It could be accepted, though, that living labs “represent an approach to user-centered innovation by engaging users in an active manner since they are considered contributors to the creative and evaluative processes in innovation and development” (ENoLL, n.d.; URB@Exp, n.d.). Living labs can be defined as partnerships between various actors -public, private, people- (Ballon & Franz, 2015; Nevens, Frantzeskaki, Gorissen, & Loorbach, 2013; Voytenko et al., 2016), where universities play a crucial role in evaluating the engagement, the exploration and the experiments in such initiatives (Evans & Karvonen, 2010; McCormick, 2017). Universities are not the only actors that have to be taken into

consideration; entrepreneurs and citizens are also an integral part of urban labs and therefore, essential in the evaluating processes (McCormick, 2017).

On the other hand, city labs are “projects in which local governments and other stakeholders jointly seek to learn about and be involved in new ways of dealing with urban challenges” (URB@Exp, n.d.). They are “initiated or at least partly supported by departments of local authorities” (Höflehner & Zimmermann, 2016; Scholl & Kemp, 2016; Scholl et al., 2017). They “generate ideas for city projects and explore visions of, for example, sustainability and governance” (Scholl & Kemp, 2016). The common concept between the two types is the production and/or implementation of innovative ideas, experimentation, co-design and learning (Höflehner & Zimmermann, 2016); the creation of a forum for innovation where interactions between different actors take place (JPI Europe, 2013). The slight differences between living labs and city labs allow for the use of the term “urban lab” to refer to both these types. M-Lab recognizes itself as a living lab, whereas Stadslab as a city lab.

Urban labs are not virtual platforms; rather they are placed in an existing geographical area (ENoLL, n.d.; Voytenko et al., 2016). Moreover, innovation and experimentation are not the only elements; participation of different actors as well as leadership⁵ are essential to make an urban lab function efficiently. It appears to be “an instrument for the active inclusion of citizens in urban projects” (Ballon & Franz, 2015). The actors’ interaction results in the creation of value, both public and private. This research focused only on the first, public value. At the same time, flexibility is crucial for a healthy cooperation among different actors, their interests and abilities (Höflehner and Zimmermann, 2016). Finally, evaluation and monitoring help the learning process of the participants and those who are interested in establishing an urban lab or just examine this new form of governance.

To sum up, there is considerable variation between urban labs. The “type of challenges they address, the way they operate, the role of research institutions as well as the

role of sustainability in the lab's agenda" (Höflechner & Zimmermann, 2016) result in the absence of one universal definition. Perhaps, it is not necessary to struggle to find the *one and unique* definition as it would alienate the "colorful" diversity of the labs. It is important though, to continue examining their role as an integral part of contemporary local governance and the challenges the latter needs to tackle towards a more balanced life.

Public Value

The concept of public value was introduced in the public sector for the first time in 1995 by Moore (Dearlove & Crainer, 2007; Meynhardt, 2009; 2017). Moore (2013) considers it as the output of a project, policy, or activity that contributes to the common good. It can be expressed in economic, social and ecological benefits, which coincide with the three pillars of sustainability (Moore, 2013; Scholl et al., 2017). He explains what should be done, therefore, it is considered a normative theory (in Meynhardt et al., 2017). He argued that public value is created when "the society is successful or unsuccessful in achieving a desired goal" and not when someone collects all the individual satisfactions (in Dearlove & Crainer, 2007). It is not clearly mentioned though, whether the level of success is decided by the society itself or by a higher authority, such as the government.

To continue, Bozeman introduced the theory of public value failure according to which, the conditions are not always generating public value. This happens when "the public sector does not provide the goods and services required to achieve public value" (Bozeman, 2007; Bryson, Crosby, & Bloomberg, 2014). Actually, there is a creation of the latter but with a negative sign. In practice, it means that the "consumers" of value are dissatisfied from the outcomes of a project or activity. But is it truly only the citizens that consume? What about the authorities or economic actors such as enterprises? It has to be noted that Bozeman has been criticized for neglecting the role of noncitizens (Bryson et al., 2014).

Furthermore, Meynhardt (2012; 2015) supports that public value is created by implementing a project, policy or other activity that generates benefits for the common good. He (2009, 2012) sees it as “the extent to which a relationship between an individual and a social entity influences the fulfillment or change of basic needs”. It has to be mentioned, though, that public interest and public value are not necessarily interlinked as the former refers to the legalist aspects of welfare and common good of the community as a whole, whereas the latter is linked to the managerial perspective of public value creation (Meynhardt, 2012). Meynhardt’s explanation remains elusive because the relation between interest and value is not clear enough.

“What is valuable for society varies over time and across cultures” (Meynhardt et al., 2017). It “tends to take shape in response to the material and social concerns that arise in a specific area” (Alford & O’Flynn, 2008; 2009), in one word its surroundings. “The facts may not necessarily lead to the same appreciation by different people” (Meynhardt, 2012). There are various definitions for the concept of public value as it happens to be the case for the urban labs as well. Personally, I receive it as the benefits and/or disadvantages⁶ for the public during the design and implementation of a project, meaning by “public”, all those legal and non-legal entities that exist, the society as a whole as well as individuals. In this intellectual turmoil, some researchers attempted to go a step further and develop a tool or method that measures the creation of “their” definition of public value.

How can we measure public value (creation)?

There have been various suggestions concerning ways of measuring public value creation. Some existed before the emergence of the concept, like Utilitarianism and Cost-benefit Analysis (CBA), whereas others have been developed particularly for public value.

Focusing on the tailored category, Moore and Meynhardt attempted to develop a Scorecard to support their theoretical approach described above. Moore presented his

Strategic Triangle⁷. According to this, “a strategy for a public-sector organization must meet three criteria: legitimacy and support, operational capability and value creation” (Alford & O’Flynn, 2008; Meynhardt et al., 2017; Moore, 2012). Public managers are responsible for trying to meet these criteria and “lead their organizations towards the production of greater public value” (Moore, 1995). The framework helps them to estimate the “constraints and responsibilities within which they work” (Williams & Shearer, 2011). However, it remains unclear “how value objectives are to be pursued” both in theory and practice (Williams & Shearer, 2011). Moore does not explain how the three criteria interrelate. How is it possible to measure public value when it serves at the same time as a means and an outcome?

Another approach is that of Meynhardt (2012; 2017), who argues that there are four different perspectives from which someone evaluates public value: moral-ethical, hedonistic-aesthetic, utilitarian-instrumental and political-social. These represent the ways one approaches the examining concept and are quite subjective as every person is characterized by their own values. Before translating the four aspects into a scorecard, Meynhardt (2012; 2015) explained that “without a financial measure, a Public Value scorecard may find no acceptance by practitioners”. Meynhardt fairly supports the idea that if something does not produce any financial benefits, decision makers and practitioners will be reluctant in taking it into consideration since it is of vital importance for justifying their policies. Hence, he added the concept of economic value to the aforementioned⁸. Then, he (2012; 2015; 2017) introduced five main questions where risks and opportunities emerge. He seeks to answer whether a project is useful, profitable, decent, politically acceptable and finally, whether it leaves space for positive experiences. The respondents are asked to “rank the five values according to their importance by answering to a number of statements. The latter provides an insight to what the public regards as valuable (Meynhardt, 2012; 2015; 2017). The Scorecard “helps to weigh future decisions and analyze risks and opportunities of public value contribution goals. It is a view of managerial actions by considering societal needs”

(Meynhardt et al., 2017). On the other hand, Meynhardt (2012) himself recognizes that every effort to measure public value “needs to be tailored to specific circumstances” due to different situations. This is not always easy, though, and usually, needs time. The method is highly subjective as it depends on personal values. It constraints to understand what is valuable for the public as such rather than only its individual parts that is, the respondents.

To sum up, “the concept of public value can help organizations to better engage with their community and to benefit from this” (Meynhardt et al., 2017). Even though it goes through the third decade of its life it remains a complex still, valid theory that needs to be developed more in order to be regarded as a mature idea (Alford, 2008; Benington, 2011). “A clear definition remains elusive” (O'Flynn, 2007), which makes it difficult to develop any measuring practices without omissions that affect its outcome. In this confusion, I attempted to develop a method that measures public value creation in urban labs and tried to overcome some of the constraints of previous efforts analysed in this chapter. Still, measuring public value requires effort and recognition that the result might still be criticized as a subjective perspective.

Chapter 3

Towards an Assessment Tool for Public Value Creation in Urban Labs

Measuring Public Value Creation

To begin with, researchers McCormick and Frantzeskaki explained that there are various ways of assessing projects, policies and activities implemented by an urban lab; they depend on the goals of each lab. Qualitative analysis seems to be easier as some concepts, such as wellbeing or entrepreneurship, can only be described. Certainly, this does not exclude the option of conducting a quantitative analysis. However, if one wants to be effective, they have to monitor such an analysis throughout the process and have a clearly defined final goal from the beginning (Frantzeskaki, personal communication, May 12, 2017). Pantopicon (Rijkens,

personal communication, May 12, 2017) underlined the necessity of considering *everyone* when evaluating a process since public value affects the society as a whole. The labs recognized the difficulties in translating intangible meanings into numbers. The projects use/used particular indices to understand their public value. These are the number of users, their satisfaction, the reputation of the project and sometimes technical means. There was no systematic way of assessing any other variables linked to public value.

The interviewees recognized the constraints of their methods and urged the importance for having one tool tailored to the urban labs' needs. At the same time though, they underlined the difficulty of creating such a tool since every urban lab and every project have their own dynamics.

Types of public value

There is no *one* type of public value that can be created. It usually depends on the aim of a policy or activity. Knowing the types of value that are pursued and those that are actually created supports the decision-making of those involved who need to know what exactly they should take into consideration concerning future decisions.

Based on empirical research, I created a list of several types. Some of the elements have been included in the main types of value created. That does not mean that it would be wrong to keep them separately, and grouping did not downgrade their worth. Thus, the integrated list became as presented in the table Types of Public Value (TPV).

For whom is this public value created?

As it has already been mentioned, public value means that the values are for the wider public namely, the society as a whole, as well as all its individual components that are members of the human community and each one has its own role and function. However, urban processes need time to be established broadly in order to include all the actors of the society. Hence, it

might be too soon to appreciate whether a value is “public” or will eventually become one (Rijkens, personal communication, May 12, 2017).

For the research, I subdivided the beneficiaries into smaller groups based on their role in a project. Hence, “local authorities” and “citizens involved” stood on their own. Moreover, “non-involved citizens” referred to individuals that have not been actively involved still, were affected by the outcomes of the project. “Urban professionals” are the economic actors of the society that had a stake, tangible or intangible. It is mainly specialists, such as private enterprises, SMEs and other companies. Finally, I added “no-one” as an option in case someone considered the examined project ineffective.

Indicators of public value creation

There are several ways to indicate public value creation. Still, it remains difficult as the indicators can be expressed both objectively and subjectively. The former is generally recognized as such. Still, there are subjective indicators that depend on one’s personal perspective. But these indices are not definite, and their meaning builds upon personal values and ideas. Certainly, a number of tools is developed in order to define the existence or absence of such concepts, but they remain descriptive and highly depended on personal viewpoints. Therefore, there cannot be a fixed list that accompanies them.

Moving to the research, some specific indicators have been identified in the literature and confirmed by the interviewees, who take them into consideration regarding their projects and decisions. Active involvement and level of satisfaction are highly linked to the main characteristics of the urban labs. All of them indicate the creation of one of the five types of value determined previously. Certainly, there might be more indicators that are either not relevant to the examined projects, therefore, not mentioned, or not taken into consideration by the initiators for practical reasons⁹.

Concerning innovation and learning, the respondents found it very difficult to define them as they argued that these specific types of value appear implicitly. In other words, they explained that knowing whether something is innovative or promotes learning is “something people can just see and feel without being able to prove it” was a common answer most of the interviewees gave. All indices can be applied to all projects, but they do not necessarily appear in every one of them because projects might not (aim to) generate them. The table Indicators (Ind.) shows those indicators that have been identified and grouped.

Tool for measuring public value creation in urban labs

Measuring public value creation is essential for understanding the impact of an urban lab project. The suggested tool consists of two main phases namely, expectation and reality. The users of the tool set their goals by indicating what they would like to see as project results at a certain moment (what ought to). These are what I called, Expected value. In the second phase, the users evaluate the current facts they are experiencing in order to examine the Real value. As a final step, one has to compare the two results and conclude about the project’s successfulness. The closer the results, the more the reality meets the expectations, which means that the project can be considered quite successful. According to the interviewees’ answers in the first section, it’s up to the decision-makers, whoever they might be, to conclude whether the results are satisfying or not since they have the final say regarding the project. In case the expected value proves to be much higher than the real one then, I would suggest the decision-makers to define how acceptable the difference is by using a deviation freedom of x%.

Since the main characteristics of a lab are among others, innovation and learning, I considered them the first priority of an urban lab project. Certainly, that does not mean that all the other elements of the table (Ind.) should be excluded or neglected. For active involvement, I used double weighting as it is one of the main characteristics of an urban lab

but only partly embraced, whereas the previous two are separate categories of value and hence, they stand on their own. Since active involvement refers to citizens, I included it in the social category.

The participants have been asked to score from -2 to 2 the indicators based on what types of value have been generated (real value) and on what they would like to see (expected value). In the second case, the indicator of satisfaction has not been taken into account as it is unfeasible to be satisfied for something that does not exist.

The result is two numbers, less or equal 2 and more or equal -2. The one represents what outcomes the respondents would like to see. The other presents the reality given by personal perceptions and estimations of the participants.

Expectation Function:

$$\{[\text{Local Income} + \text{Competition} + \text{Entrepreneurship} + \text{Cooperation}] / 4 + [\text{Energy Efficiency} + \text{Resource Efficiency} + \text{Environmental Quality}] / 3 + [\text{Community Wellbeing} + \text{Social Relationships} + \text{Active Involvement} * 2 + \text{Satisfaction}] / 4 + \text{Innovation} + \text{Learning}\} / 5$$

Reality Function:

$$\{[\text{Local Income} + \text{Competition} + \text{Entrepreneurship} + \text{Cooperation}] / 4 + [\text{Energy Efficiency} + \text{Resource Efficiency} + \text{Environmental Quality}] / 3 + [\text{Community Wellbeing} + \text{Social Relationships} + \text{Active Involvement} * 2 + \text{Satisfaction}] / 5 + \text{Innovation} + \text{Learning}\} / 5$$

The decision-makers derive conclusions based on a pre-defined deviation freedom. If the expectations exceed the reality beyond the allowed limits, the project could be considered unsatisfying or even failed. This refers to Bozeman's suggestion that inadequate conditions lead to dissatisfaction and public value failure (Bozeman, 2007).

Before moving to the next chapter, I provide an example in order to make the concept of deviation freedom more understandable. Hence, in case the expected value was much higher than the real one then, the decision-makers had to define how acceptable the difference was. Assuming that the real value was 1.12 and the expected 1.32, the difference

would equal 0.2. In other words, the real value would be 15.15% less than expected. So far, everything remains neutral. If the decision-makers defined a deviation freedom of 5%, the results would be dissatisfying. Still, if their deviation freedom is looser, for example 20%, the minimum acceptable would be at 1.056. in that case, real value would be within the acceptable limits.

Example: Real Value = 1.12
Expected Value = 1.32

Difference: 0.2

The next chapter applies the assessment method to four urban lab projects and helps understand its usage.

Chapter 4

Public value creation in practice & Comparative Analysis

Chapter 4 applies the method to four urban lab projects and compares their results. The examined cases are Brandweerkazerne, Operatie Steenbreek, Amador and 500 Woningen Renoveren. Every project has/had its own characteristics and aims. This chapter compares the results regarding the four urban lab projects. It examines similarities and differences concerning the sub-questions. At the same time, it explains some remarkable results. To begin with, four projects have been examined of which, two have already been completed namely, Brandweerkazerne and Amador. Operatie Steenbreek and 500 Woningen Renoveren are still ongoing. All of them generated more than two kinds of value. Brandweerkazerne aimed to enhance mainly social values by creating a meeting space for individuals, urban professionals and any other actor that might be interested. Operatie Steenbreek intends to enhance environmental awareness and green the city. Similarly, 500 Woningen Renoveren

points at improving energy and resource efficiency of households. Finally, Amador's main goals were strengthening of social relationships and greener thinking in terms of reduced meat consumption.

According to the results shown in the table Types & Indicators (T&Ind), most of the projects contributed to social public value, learning and innovation. Only 500 Woningen Renoveren supported environmental value at a high level, whereas Operatie Steenbreek, which also aimed at greener activities, ranked this type only at the fourth place. As explained by Beumer (personal communication, April 10, 2017), the project involved mainly private yards. Greening private properties is possible even without external support. The project's novelty that has been considered more important was its social aspect. Exchanging pavement with plants turned out to be an opportunity for meeting people. Economic public value has also been supported on a smaller scale with only exception the case of Operatie Steenbreek, where it received a slight negative sign. Project leaders van Wanroij and Vandermosten (van Wanroij, personal communication, May 3, 2017; Vandermosten, personal communication, May 10, 2017) explained that the main reason for low economic value creation is explained due to the urban labs' goals. They argued that the local authorities have other departments responsible for the economic development. Thus, the urban labs should focus mainly on other kinds of value.

Considering the indices, satisfaction, cooperation and social relationships have received the highest grades. In contrast, the indicators that appeared less, according to the respondents, were local income, competition, energy and resource efficiency. The indicators are highly interlinked to the types of value that have been generated. Since every project differed, it was reasonable to expect distinct results regarding the indicators. The table Indicators of Public Value (Ind.PV) present which indicators and sub-indicators appeared in each project.

Inclusion of citizens in urban lab projects is a main characteristic, which supports the participation of different types of stakeholders. A common line concerning the beneficiaries' groups was the unequal distribution of benefits. Hence, the first category that received most of the benefits has been the actively involved citizens followed by urban professionals. Local authorities and individuals affected by the outcomes of the project have also gained some slight profits, though not as much as the previous groups. In relation to the "no-one" group, all respondents gave a negative or neutral answer, which led to negative results. Interpreting the numbers showed that all the examined projects generated several kinds of public value that benefitted at least one group of beneficiaries. It appears that the higher the level of involvement, the more the benefits one receives, which contrasts to the notion of "public" value. At this point, it is important to remind that not all values are public but may eventually become in the future. For example, in Operatie Steenbreek the involved citizens transformed their own properties by replacing their pavement with plants. Private value had been generated as the garden owners were benefitting by the changes. After a while, though, non-participants and urban professionals started realizing the public values created, such as social and learning. Therefore, the element of time should be taken into consideration when making decisions (Rijkens, personal communication, May 12, 2017). The most contentious results appeared in Brandweerkazerne and Operatie Steenbreek because of the responses' high dispersion regarding "non-involved citizens" and "local authorities" adequately. In these cases, half of the respondents scored highly negatively and the rest highly positively. The answers proved the difficulty to understand who is a public-value "consumer" at a certain moment. The group that scored the lowest after no-one was the local authorities in the Amador case. One possible reason is the project's origins. It was initiated by an individual citizen that wanted to contribute to the local community. Stadslab was involved by having an advisory role but the main target group was the citizens of Antwerp. Hence, there was no

much involvement from the side of the authorities. The results are presented in the table Project Beneficiaries (PB).

One goal of the research was to develop a method/tool that measures public value creation. It consisted of two main phases which refer to the existing and the desirable situation. After finding the expected and the real value for every project¹⁰ (see table Projects' Expected & Real Public Value - PERPV), it was necessary to reflect on the results. Only Amador achieved to generate real value higher than expected. The remaining projects had higher expectations. In 500 Woningen Renoveren the gap was relatively small that is, around 11%. In contrast, Brandweerkazerne and Operatie Steenbreek had bigger differences namely, 57% and 47.41% adequately.

There are several reasons that explain the big percentages in Brandweerkazerne and Operatie Steenbreek. Regarding the difficulties of the first project, there is a lack of motivation as the renting costs are relatively high and the interested actors are not able and/or willing to pay. In addition, some participants argued that there is also a lack of activities on a regular basis, which could enhance the involvement of more actors. Furthermore, it has been criticized for lack of transparency driven by the decisions of the elite, meaning the local authorities who own the building (van der Linden, personal communication, May 31, 2017). Lastly, it is usually thought that authorities, as owners, have the means to achieve more than other interest groups, which results in higher expectations from the evaluators. Considering Operatie Steenbreek, the initiator explained that the main difficulties are exchanging information about everyone's progress and controlling the process since the project refers to private properties (Beumer, personal communication, April 10, 2017). From the side of the research, I could not reach the citizens due to data protection, therefore, most of the respondents were volunteers of a team that supports the project. Before filling the questionnaire, they explained that they would be relatively strict because the project was still ongoing at that moment.

One could assume that Stadslab's projects are more successful than those of M-Lab. From a first sight, it seems true. However, every urban lab has its own criteria to evaluate and decide upon such matters. M-Lab's expectations could be considered "too optimistic", as well as Stadslab's opinion regarding the real value of their projects. Similarly, it might be the opposite case: M-Lab's projects might be "too pessimistic" when scoring the real value and Stadslab could be too modest with low expectations. Whatever the case, each urban lab has its own dynamics and if compared to other labs, it should be taken into consideration that there are some differences in the way they operate and develop ideas, as well as in the challenges they address. To conclude, the results show the potential differences and/or similarities between projects with divergent goals. The participants' roles affect the outcomes, while external policies and activities might determine the projects' goals and directions. Urban labs do not exist separately from the world; rather they are an integral part of what is called "urban community".

Chapter 5

Conclusions & Future Research

Urban labs are a new form of governance that appeared as part of a solution to the emerging urban challenges. One of their main objectives is to enhance the co-creation of public value by embracing all stakeholders in an active manner. The article examined how, what kind and for whom urban labs create public value and presented a method that measures its production. Regarding the latter, one has to find the types of value and the indicators generated in a project. In pursuit of examining how "public" the values are, one has to find which stakeholders receive the benefits. Further, the researcher calculated the expected and the real value and compared the results in order to examine how much has been achieved based on what was expected. The results showed that only Amador managed to generate real value higher than expected. The remaining projects had higher expectations. The level of

successfulness depends on a deviation freedom. Stadslab's projects had lower expectations compared to those of M-Lab's. Brandweerkazerne's building is a public property, which explains the high anticipations from the evaluators. Operatie Steenbreek is still ongoing, which combined with a few difficulties in controlling the process, results in a big difference between the real and the expected value. Can one consider the projects successful or failed based on these results? The answer is negative. The person or group that is responsible for the project and more specifically, the actors that have been chosen to assess the project's successfulness, analyze the outcome having in mind a deviation freedom, which helps them to determine whether the results are satisfying or not. For example, if the deviation freedom was 5%, all the projects except Amador would fail. On the contrary, if the deviation freedom was 15%, 500 Woningen Renoveren would also be successful. Moreover, the results depend on the number of respondents. The more the answers, the higher the possibilities of having a better insight into the project's progress. 500 Woningen Renoveren had only 4 responses, whereas Amador 20. Comparing these two, one could have a better understanding of the latter as it offers a wider range of perspectives. Furthermore, some participants explained that since the project they had to grade was still ongoing during the time of the research, they could not answer very positively because they needed to know the final outcomes. Thus, they claimed high expectations but remained modest when they evaluated the current situation. During a project, it is possible to await new developments and, therefore, expect more. On the contrary, once the project has been completed, the evaluators know that there is no much to anticipate anymore. As a result, they either soften their standards or are more indulgent about the projects' performance. It would be helpful, though, to apply the assessment during the implementation of a project as well and adjust its direction -if necessary- before its completion.

It is essential to mention a few characteristics before moving to the next paragraph. Weighting of indicators and/or beneficiaries is optional and depends on the needs defined

during the different stages of a project. In this research, the weighting procedure, as well as the indicators, have been based on the information provided by the interviewees. I applied a double weighting only to one indicator following the respondents' opinion on its importance. If more indices had been calculated double then, returning to no weighting would produce essentially disparate results. Considering the respondents, the grading procedure started as subjective since they gave their personal opinion as it happens with Meynhardt's scorecard but gradually became intersubjective as I found the weighted averages. Grading was affected by the role the actor plays/played but at the same time, by their identity (personal background, culture) and their surroundings. Finally, measuring indicators is relevant. Contrary to Moore's Strategic Triangle which presents three pre-defined criteria for measuring public value, I argue that there are numerous ways for calculating the same object. Therefore, it's up to the decision-makers or in general, the users of the method to choose what to take into consideration since it's their way of approaching the examining issue.

During the research, most of the interviewees urged the necessity for having a clearer tool or method to support their efforts in measuring public values. Thus, the introduced method could be very helpful in their future assessments. As mentioned previously, I based the approach on the collected data. Its application might differ to other projects. Still, it remains flexible and can be adapted as it leaves space for changes. One can add or remove indicators or even kinds of value if it's considered necessary. At the same time, it is possible to adapt the weighting system to every occasion. It depends on the needs and the goals of the project. It is up to the person or team who has the final say. To note, the functions I introduced can be applied to every stage of the project's design and implementation. There is no need to wait for its completion. Indeed, examining evaluations during the design and implementation stages would support decision-makers in their next steps.

On the contrary, some difficulties appeared when I applied the method to the four cases. The grading system tries to quantify the examining elements, which is not always

possible since there are some qualitative concepts that are difficult to be rated. For example, competition, community wellbeing and social relationships. Moreover, the respondents answered based on their personal opinion, which on the one hand helps to understand the different perspectives; on the other though, it leads to subjective results. This means that a different sample could give disparate results. I partly solved this issue by calculating the weighted averages. Finally, it was not easy to reach individuals mainly due to data protection or unwillingness to cooperate even though the questionnaires were anonymous. Similarly, the initiators were extremely time constrained, therefore, I had to strictly control the interviews to avoid any overtime. Still, the interviewees were very helpful on the latter and knew exactly what they wanted to say, and they provided me clear and coherent information. Despite the difficulties, the method provided an important insight into the projects' performance.

Considering the method, there were two main limitations. Firstly, there was a lack of indicators regarding innovation and learning. Some respondents argued that there are no indicators besides common sense. They recognized only a few indices, which I did not use as such because of their qualitative nature. The second limitation was the high dependence on the decision-makers. If the team is not a fair representation of the society, it risks of being criticized as an elite who is interested only for the few.

There are ways for improving the method. To begin with, it would be essential to introduce more indicators, especially for the values of innovation and learning. The former could be measured by the level of improvement and interdisciplinarity. Innovation appears when a project contributes to the amelioration of a situation and/or combines different educational backgrounds in pursuit of achieving a desired goal. Moreover, learning had only one indicator, that of awareness. Personal knowledge creation and behavioral change are equally important. Finally, participation – referred as “active involvement” in the research – could be assessed by the level of involvement as presented in the second chapter: co-creation, exploration-experimentation and evaluation. The more the indicators, the more the

information regarding the values generated, which could provide a useful insight for future analyses and decisions. Moreover, having a bigger sample would increase the level of reliability. The more people provide their opinion, the higher the chances for resulting intersubjective outcomes, which lead to a better understanding of the examining case. Furthermore, it would be essentially helpful to distinguish the indicators according to their time scale, meaning the moment they start becoming recognized. Values are not always public at the moment they are generated but might eventually become by gradually affecting more actors in the society. It is a matter of time and has to be taken into consideration while judging how “public” something can be today and in the future. In other words, it is important to distinguish the indicators that emerge in the short-term from those that appear after some time. I consider it an integral part of the method as it would help to understand and explain the results in more depth. Finally, it is important to consider the decision-makers. *Who* decides depends on the project and the structure of the urban lab. Some leave the decision to all the participants, whereas others prefer a smaller group of 5-10 people. There is no “one” best option. However, it should be clear “who” and “how” one decides about the project as their judgement affects its future.

To conclude, the suggested method should be seen as a flexible approach because it has been developed for dynamic processes, these of urban lab projects. The method developed in the article needs also further research. Adding more indicators to the existing ones, especially regarding learning and innovation, would enhance the method’s efficiency¹¹. Thus, what indicators could be included in the method? It is also important, to find ways of incorporating indicators that are purposely neglected due to their qualitative nature. Quantitative means, such as calculators, are not always able to substitute qualitative notions, for instance, wellbeing and happiness. Hence, developing a qualitative measurement would support the creation of a heterogeneous approach without underestimating the qualitative elements. Multi-criteria analysis could be a helpful tool but needs to be accompanied by

additional means if one explores the potentialities of a project. Finally, one of the main aims of an urban lab is co-creation of values and participation of multiple stakeholders. It is not clear though, which participatory method is more suitable for urban lab projects. Further exploration of this field would improve the active involvement of various actors and reinforce the creation of public value in urban lab projects. The method's outcomes as such will not provide a definite answer; it depends on the approach its users adopted when they decided to design, implement, evaluate or just examine a project. What should be kept in mind is that urban lab projects are dynamic processes that need to be assessed in every step of their progress.

Footnotes

1. Four projects in total.
2. A centre open to the public responsible for providing information regarding environmental and energy issues.
3. The number, of course, depends on the type of project since some do not allow the participation of many people at the time of this research. Citizens are also included.
4. The research focused only on living labs and city labs because the case-study labs acknowledge themselves as either living labs or city labs.
5. In terms of proper coordination and management.
6. Disadvantages as I recognize the potential existence of Bozeman's negative public value.
7. It has to be mentioned that, at first, the Strategic Triangle was a theoretical tool that acted as a guide for public managers. Only, in 2013 Moore introduced a checklist of values that transformed the Triangle into a Scorecard (Meynhardt et al., 2017).
8. Certainly, the economic aspect can be considered part of the utilitarian-instrumental value, but Meynhardt believes that since it is one of the motivating powers of human society, it has to hold a distinct position.
9. Some indicators are difficult to be expressed quantitatively and qualitative assessment options are not always favored by the initiators regarding their decision making. Hence, sometimes it is preferable to exclude them or better, exchange them with quantifiable means.
10. Using the two functions presented in the previous chapter.
11. Such as level of improvement and interdisciplinarity for innovation; personal knowledge creation and behavioral change for learning; and as presented in the second chapter, co-creation, exploration-experimentation and evaluation for "active involvement".

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Tables

Types of Public Value (TPV)	
Types	Includes
Economic	-
Environmental	-
Social	Political, Strategic, Quality of Life, Ideological, Stewardship, Institutional-Governance
Innovation	Physical Outcomes
Learning	Awareness

Indicators (Ind.)		
Types of Public Value	Indicators	Description
Economic	Local Income	Any kind of monetary impact: positive or negative change, money invested
	Competition	Economic rivalry among actors with monetary interest
	Entrepreneurship	Business development
	Cooperation	Cooperation for economic profit
Environmental	Energy Efficiency	Proper use of energy, Measured with technical means
	Resource Efficiency	Proper use of natural resources, Measured with technical means
	Environmental Quality	Environmental conditions that differ among ecosystems. There are various aspects like: biodiversity, air quality, soil quality and water quality
Social	Community wellbeing	There are numerous ways of approaching such a concept. Based on the interviews, it is linked to people's psychology, the feeling of being safe
	Social relationships	Development and/or enhancement of human interactions, networking
	Active Involvement	Participation in the design, implementation and/or evaluation process of a project
	Satisfaction-Successfulness	Being happy for the outcomes and/or the progress one notices regarding a project
Innovation	Physical Outcomes	Tangible developments, for example building renovation
	Prototype Idea	Novelty, action that has not been implemented before
Learning	Awareness	Being informed and eager to change personal behavior towards a certain goal

Type & Indicators (T&Ind)		Projects									
Type of Public Value	Indicators	Brandweerkazerne		Operatie Steenbreek		Amador		500 Woningen Renoveren			
		Weighted Average	Average	Weighted Average	Average	Weighted Average	Average	Weighted Average	Average	Weighted Average	Average
Economic	Local Income	0.461	0.615	-1.125	-0.156	0.235	0.65	1	1		
	Competition	0.153		-1.375		-0.058		1			
	Entrepreneurship	0.923		0.25		1.058		0.75			
	Cooperation	0.923		1.625		1.368		1.25			
Environmental	Energy Efficiency	-0.538	-0.343	0	0.5	0.764	0.923	1.75	1.583		
	Resource Efficiency	-0.416		0		1.058		1.5			
	Environmental Quality	-0.076		1.5		0.947		1.5			
Social	Community Wellbeing	0.923	0.828	1.25	1.343	1.1	1.343	1.5	1.125		
	Social Relationships	1.076		1.5		1.368		1			
	Active Involvement	0.083		1.375		1.157		1.25			
	Satisfaction-Successfulness	1.23		1.25		1.75		0.75			
Innovation	-	0.692	0.692	1.125	1.125	1.055	1.055	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Learning	-	0.833	0.833	0.75	0.75	1.058	1.058	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25

The numbers range from -2 to 2

Indicators of Public Value (Ind.PV)				
Indicators & Sub-indicators	Amador	Brandweerkazerne	Operatie Steenbreek	500 Woningen Renoveren
• Satisfaction-Success	X	X	X	X
• Expectation				X
• Local Income		X		
– Money Invested	X			X
• Competition		X		X
• Cooperation	X	X	X	X
• Entrepreneurship	X	X		X
• Energy Efficiency				X
– Technical Means ¹				X
• Resource Efficiency				X
– Technical Means				X
• Environmental Quality			X	
– Water capture			X	
– Biodiversity			X	
– Heat Warming Effect			X	
– Air Quality			X	
• Community Wellbeing	X	X	X	X
– Citizens' Psychology			X	
• Social Relationships	X	X	X	
• Citizens' Active Involvement	X		X	X
• Physical Outcomes		X	X	X
• Prototyping	X	X	X	X
• Awareness	X		X	X

¹ Technical means are used both in resource and energy efficiency.

Projects' Beneficiaries (PB)

Projects				
Beneficiaries	Brandweerkazerne	Operatie Steenbreek	Amador	500 Woningen Renoveren
Weighted Average				
Local Authorities	0.636	0.428	-0.411	1.333
Urban Professionals	0.909	1.142	0.062	1
Citizens Involved	0.727	1.142	1.11	2
Non-involved Citizens	-0.083	0.142	0.266	1
No-one	-1.916	-2	-1.625	-2

The numbers range from -2 to 2

Projects' Expected & Real Public Value (PERPV)

Projects									
Type of Public Value	Brandweerkazerne		Operatie Steenbreek		Amador		500 Woningen Renoveren		
	Expected	Real	Expected	Real	Expected	Real	Expected	Real	
Economic	0.909	0.615	0.718	-0.156	0.719	0.65	0.937	1	
Environmental	1.178	-0.343	1.375	0.5	1.01	0.923	1.416	1.583	
Social	1.121	0.679	1.562	1.35	1.267	1.425	1.437	1.15	
Innovation	1.384	0.692	1.5	1.125	1	1.055	1.75	1.5	
Learning	1.166	0.833	1.625	0.75	1	1.058	1.75	1.25	
Total	1.151	> 0.495	1.356	> 0.713	0.999	< 1.022	1.458	> 1.296	

The numbers range from -2 to 2

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Author: Katerina Antoniadis

Corresponding Author:

Katerina Antoniadis, Independent Researcher
+306986310857, +31(0)686368471
antoniadis.kateriko@gmail.com